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Gianangeli A., Di Giuseppe E., D'Orazio M. *“Mould growth risk evaluation of internal insulation solutions in a historic building under temperate climates”*.

The definitive version is available at / La versione definitiva è disponibile in:

SER4SC 2018 Seismic and Energy Renovation for Sustainable Cities - Conference Proceedings. 2018. Pages 508-517, Giuseppe Margani, Gianluca Rodonò, Vincenzo Sapienza (editors), Edicom Edizioni, ISBN: 978-88-96386-56-9.

Abstract

Retrofit interventions in historic building's envelope usually involve internal thermal insulation. Several authors show how this intervention could affect internal hygrometric conditions and cause mould growth especially in cold climate. Mould growth risk could be enhanced by specific installation conditions, as the necessity of wet bonding surfaces for a better adhesion of particular insulation typologies, which may determine high water contents in the envelope materials for long time.

This paper reports the results of the hygrothermal experimental assessment of two internal insulation systems (one based on a capillary active insulation and the other one on a synthetic insulation) installed on the wall of a historic building in a temperate climate. Indoor and outdoor environmental conditions, as well as temperature and relative humidity in each layer of the renovated wall, have been detected for almost one year. Obtained results demonstrate that high water content in the wall surfaces and interfaces may last for a long time after the insulation installation and cannot be disregarded, as it can be very influential on the historic materials decay and mould growth risk.

Keywords

historic building, internal thermal insulation, hygrothermal behavior, mould growth risk

Introduction

Internal thermal insulation is a typical energy-saving measure that allows to preserve the original exterior architectural facades of historic buildings [1, 2]. A wide range of insulation materials is available on the market and in recent years new materials have been developed at this scope [3], e.g. vacuum insulation panels (VIPs) [4], aerogel insulation [5] and capillary active thermal insulation materials [6], next to the traditional ones as rock wool and expanded polystyrene.

Insulation systems can be categorized based on specific physical properties or installation configurations. A specific classification, considering their potential use on historic facades, is also based on the capillary activity of the systems and distinguish between capillary active and non-capillary active insulation systems. Capillary active insulation systems consist of a capillary active insulation material (i.e. calcium silicate, wood fiber insulation) in combination with a glue mortar. The capillary active insulation is able to absorb the liquid water and redistribute it inwards (towards the room) by a liquid flow that follows the inwards capillary pressure gradient [6, 7]. On the contrary, non-capillary active systems can be vapour open or vapour tight. Vapour tight systems can be obtained based on a vapour tight insulation material (i.e. PUR, XPS, cellular glass) or based on a vapour open material (i.e. mineral wool) in combination with a vapour barrier.

There is still a lack of knowledge about the performance of building elements after the application of internal insulation under various conditions, especially in historic

buildings. In fact, the application of an interior insulation could significantly change the hygrothermal behavior of the wall [8] and induce damages to the existing wall structure [9]: e.g. mould growth [10, 11] on surfaces, dry rot of any embedded wooden structures [12], or frost spalling of the original facade material [13]. Mould growth can result in a degradation of building materials [14] and can negatively influence the occupant's health [15, 16].

In order to assess the mould risk on building materials, several mould prediction models are available in literature, e.g. temperature ratio, Isopleth systems, biohygrothermal model, ESP-r mould prediction model, empirical VTT-model, etc. A well-known one is the Sedlbauer's Isopleth model [17], which is frequently applied in the building physics field to evaluate this specific risk. As relative humidity and temperature are the main mould inducing factors in this model, the mould risk is expressed by Isopleth curves based on these conditions, which separate favorable from unfavorable conditions for the mould growth. The conditions below which no spore germination or growth will occur, are indicated by the LIM (Lowest Isopleth for Mould)-curve.

Another potential risk for internally insulated historic walls is the biochemical deterioration of the external envelope caused by the appearance of stains due to the biofouling of algae [18], with the consequent aesthetic damage for the facades. Actually, very few studies attempted to model biofouling on building materials, and further researches are needed to predict the algae growth on facades [19, 20].

Considering the limited knowledge on the effects of internal insulation on historical facades in temperate climates, this research investigates the consequences of the installation of alternative internal insulation solutions, including capillary and non-capillary active materials, on a historic public building, located in a temperate climate (Ancona-Italy), through an on-site hygrothermal monitoring.

The historic building case study

The historic building case study is the “Rectorate Palace”, a late Nineteenth-century palace located in Ancona (Italy). The building has a quite regular shape, with a floor plan of about 920 m². It is four-storey high and structured around a central courtyard.

Fig. 1. (a) main facade of the building “Rectorate Palace”; (b) internal courtyard

According to the Italian climates classification, the building is located in the climatic zone D, which is characterized by 14.5°C as average yearly outdoor temperature, 1688°C heating degree days (base temperature of 19°C) and a heating period of 166 days.

An energy retrofitting intervention on the whole building is planned to start in 2020 and will consist in the internal insulation of the envelope and the heating equipments renovation. To evaluate the impacts of different insulation solutions as preliminary test, this research activity compares two insulation systems installed in a North-West oriented room of 16 m² at the first floor. The two insulation systems are a capillary active system (Calcium Silicate) and a vapour tight insulation (XPS + gypsum plasterboard).

The thicknesses of each insulation material were determined considering the actual Italian Regulations on building energy efficiency, in particular D.M. 26.06.15 [21]. For the climatic zone D, the transmittance limit value is $U = 0,32 \text{ W/m}^2 \text{ K}$. Considering the available insulation thickness on the market, a total of 13 cm of CaSi insulation and 8 cm of XPS insulation were selected. This choice allows to obtain almost the same thermal transmittance value for the building wall ($U = 0,28 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$), which consisted on 67 cm of load bearing masonry plastered on both sides.

The calcium silicate insulation system consisted on a total of 13 cm of CaSi insulation (5+5+3cm), uniformly glued with mortar to ensure a perfect adhesion with the old wall surface, and 0,5 cm of internal plaster. The XPS insulation system consisted on 8 cm of XPS insulation, punctually glued with adhesive mortar, and a gypsum plasterboard of 1,25 cm.

Methodology

The monitoring activity aimed to collect the hygrothermal data of the insulated wall and the boundary conditions represented by the indoor climate and outside climate. The installation of the monitoring sensors was performed in parallel with the insulation intervention. In this way temperature and relative humidity sensors were installed in closed air gaps in the interface of the different material layers of the systems: between the old masonry and the insulation panels; between the XPS-insulation panel and the gypsum plasterboard. For both insulation systems, sensors were also installed on the internal and external side of the wall surfaces. In figure 2 the sensors location in the capillary active system (figure 2a) and in the non-capillary active system (figure 2b) is represented.

Fig.2 (a) sensors position in the wall insulated with CaSi; (b) sensors position in the wall insulated with XPS.

Low power Sensirion SHT31D sensors were used to measure the relative humidity (precision $\pm 2\%$; operative range $0\div 100\%$) and the temperature (accuracy $\pm 0,3^\circ\text{C}$; operative range $-40\div 125^\circ\text{C}$). They were connected via I2C protocol to a 16 bit data logger device NI myRIO-1900. Additional SHT31D sensors were installed in the middle of the room to measure the indoor environmental conditions (temperature and relative humidity) (figure 3a). A DAVIS Vantage II Pro weather station (figure 3b) was positioned in the terrace just outside the insulated wall to collect data on the outdoor temperature (precision $\pm 0,3^\circ\text{C}$; operative range $-40\div 65^\circ\text{C}$), outdoor relative humidity (precision $\pm 2\%$ and operative range $0\div 100\%$), solar radiation (resolution $1/\text{Wm}^2$; precision $\pm 5\%$), wind speed and direction (resolution $0,4 \text{ m/s}$; precision 1 m/s) and wind driven rain (plate collector $25\times 25 \text{ cm}$; resolution $0,2 \text{ mm}$). All measurements were recorded every 10 minutes and data collection started in October 2016, immediately after the insulation intervention.

Fig. 3. (a) installation of the temperature and relative humidity sensors on the interior surface of the capillary active system (left) and the non-capillary active system (right); (b) weather station installed in the terrace for the outdoor climate monitoring

As the building is located in the climatic zone D, the conventional building heating period established by national law goes from 1st of November to 15th of April, for a maximum of 12 hours a day. In November and December 2016 the building was subjected to general maintenance works. As a consequence, the employees were moved to a different office building and the heating system was turned off. In order to reproduce the usual hygrothermal conditions of a public office, in the monitored room two Vinco YJ-A1 oil radiators (1500W) were installed and turned on from 6 a.m. to 18 p.m., with a temperature set-point of 20°C. A DeLonghi VH400 humidifier was positioned in the middle of the room to reproduce the amount of moisture usually produced by an employ in 8 hours of light activity (a total of 0,5 L per day) based on [22, 23].

Table 1 provides information on the yearly monitoring 4 sub-periods identified. The period P1 started with the conclusion of the insulation installation and ended when the building was evacuated. In P2 the heating system was turned off and the interior conditions were not controlled. In P3 the radiators and the humidifier were installed in the monitored room to reestablish the normal climatic conditions of the workspace. The last period, P4, started in spring when the eating system was turned off and ended in September 2017.

Table 1. Yearly monitoring 4 sub-periods identified

Period	Season	Heating system	Date
P1	Autumn	OFF	17/10/16 - 30/10/16
P2	Winter	OFF	30/10/17 - 09/01/17
P3	Winter	ON	09/01/17 - 15/04/17
P4	Spring and summer	OFF	15/04/17 - 30/09/17

The analysis of the monitoring data for both the insulation systems was carried also based on the Isopleth model, developed by Sedlbauer [17], to assess the mould risk on the wall surfaces. The correlation of temperature and relative humidity values, required by the model as input, was evaluated considering the Isopleth LIM II as safety limit. The Isopleth LIM II, according to Sedlbauer's substrate categories, is the curve considered for building materials with porous structure such as renderings, mineral building material, certain woods as well as insulation material [17].

Results

The indoor and outdoor temperatures and the solar radiation trends detected are reported in figure 4, according to the monitoring periods identified in table 1. In the first period, P1, the average outdoor temperature was about 18°C. The period P2 corresponds to the first two months of the winter season, in which the outside temperature progressively decreased reaching, in December, the average value of about 7°C. In this period the heating system was turned off and consequently indoor temperatures decreased to a minimum of about 6.5°C. During P3 (from the beginning of January 2017), the heating equipment was installed in the monitored room. The first weeks of that period were needed to heat the entire air volume of the room. Then, from half February, the indoor temperature was within the range of 18÷22°C. The last analyzed period, P4, represents the summer period, when the heating system was turned off. It was characterized by a very hot summer and, as a consequence, also the indoor temperatures detected were quite high (more than 30°C).

Fig. 4. Indoor and outdoor temperature and solar radiation trends during the whole yearly monitoring period

In figure 5, temperature, relative humidity and calculated vapor pressure trends at the interface between the masonry and the insulation systems are reported. During the first months, after the installation operation, a very high relative humidity was detected (higher than 95%) for both systems. In particular in the capillary active system it reached an approximate value of 99% RH, which remained stable for almost one month in P1 and P2. Then in the second half of P2 it progressively decreased, reaching values under 80% RH. On the contrary, on the XPS system the relative humidity detected was lower, with values between 83 and 95% RH during P1 and P2.

In general, it can be noticed that relative humidity decreased more quickly in the CaSi system, than in the XPS system, to a minimum value of 54% RH during the summer season. On the contrary, the XPS insulation system, showed lower relative humidity values than the CaSi insulation during the winter period (P1, P2 and P3), but higher values with a constant trend during the summer period P4. In fact, during P4, the XPS insulation maintained the relative humidity quite constant, in a range between 70 and 80%.

Fig. 5. Temperature (top), relative humidity (middle) and vapour pressure (bottom) trends during the monitored period.

The relative humidity of the air gaps between the existing masonry and the internal insulation were analyzed to evaluate the mould risk by the use of Isoleth LIM II, considering a possible air circulation in the gaps due to point-to-point glue connections. Results are reported both for the CaSi system and the XPS system in figure 6, respectively on the left and the right graphs. The monitored periods are identified with different colors: P1 in black (autumn season with heating system OFF), P2 in yellow (winter season with heating system OFF), P3 in red (winter season with heating system ON) and P4 in blue (spring and summer season with heating system OFF).

Fig. 6. Evaluation of the mould risk using the Isopleth LIM II on the internal surface of the CaSi insulation system (graphs on the left) and XPS insulation finished with plasterboard (graphs on the right)

Fig. 7. Evaluation of the hygrothermal conditions on the external surface of the CaSi insulation system (graphs in the left column) and XPS insulation finished with plasterboard (graphs in the right column)

The recorded values of temperature and relative humidity showed a similar situation for both the CaSi and the XPS systems. The non-capillary active insulation seems to perform slightly better than the capillary active one because, for all the periods, points in the graphs are more distant from the LIM II than the case of the capillary active system. The riskiest periods are P1 (black) and P2 (yellow), when the measured values are near to the Isopleth LIM II. However, for the analyzed case study, which is located in a temperate climate, no particular problems are detected on the internal surface of the walls.

Internal insulation could also affect the hygrothermal behavior of the external surface of the existing wall. Figure 7 reports the temperature and relative humidity values collected on that surface during the 4 monitoring sub-periods. It can be noticed a worse condition on this side of the wall. Due to the climate condition recorded, a significant risk of microorganism growth can be found considering the high relative humidities reached. On the external surface of buildings algae and cyanobacteria could proliferate in case of high moisture content. This aspect will be further analyzed in the future with specific models able to take into account algae growth [19].

Conclusions

The aim of this research is to investigate the hygrothermal performance of a capillary active insulation system based on CaSi and a non-capillary active system with XPS and plasterboard, installed on a historic building wall, in order to determine a possible mould growth risk.

For several months after the construction phase, the accumulated moisture content in the wall assemblies with a capillary active system was higher than in case of the vapor tight insulation system with XPS. This is probably due to the installation conditions, which requires wet wall surfaces before the CaSi panels application. However, during the summer season, the capillary active system, which allows the vapor to interchange between the masonry and the indoor environment, showed a lower relative humidity at the interface between the insulation panels and the masonry wall, in the range between 50 and 70% RH. On the contrary, the non-capillary active insulation system with XPS showed in that period higher humidity values, between 70 and 80% RH. The high relative humidity in the interface between the historical façade and installed insulations could affect indoor air quality and increase mould exposure in case of air gaps between existing masonry and insulation systems due to point-to-point connections, e.g. in case on wooden beams ends.

The mould growth risk for the building envelope was assessed using the Sedlbauer's model Isopleth LIM II curve, analyzing the temperature and relative humidity values on the internal wall surfaces. Results demonstrated that in temperate climate conditions, for the hygrothermal conditions detected during the monitoring activity, no specific mould growth problems occurs, even if the recorded values are very close to the Isopleth limit curve.

Acknowledgements

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 637268.

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